

DMP Resource efficiency solutions for circular bioeconomy

Version 1

Description

DMP for Fundamental and Applied research project "Resource efficiency solutions for circular bioeconomy"

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Izp-2024/1 0340

Researchers

Dace Lauka (0000-0002-0267-0580), Anna Kubule (0000-0002-0518-3163), Krista Laktuka (0000-0002-5658-1559), Ilze Vamža (orcid:0000-0001-8333-0838), Dagnija Blumberga (0000-0002-9712-0804)

Organizations
Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: DMP Resource efficiency solutions for circular bioeconomy

Description:

DMP for Fundamental and Applied research project "Resource efficiency solutions for circular bioeconomy"

Researchers:

Dace Lauka (0000-0002-0267-0580)

Anna Kubule (0000-0002-0518-3163)

Krista Laktuka (0000-0002-5658-1559)

Ilze Vamža (orcid:0000-0001-8333-0838)

Dagnija Blumberga (0000-0002-9712-0804)

Organizations:

Riga Technical University

Contact: Kubule Anna (anna.kubule@rtu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: lzp-2024/1 0340

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-03-26

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

To promote knowledge-intensive bioeconomy and achieve the added value increase production of high added value bioproducts should be fostered, especially, at regional scope. To promote in targeted way a wider development of the bioeconomy at the regional level, a resource efficiency toolbox based on scientifically based research methods, modeling and leveraging the county-specific competitive advantage will be created. The toolbox development will involve the use of primary and secondary data, that will be collected within the project activities. Part of those data include statistical data described here.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data is to collect a comprehensive set of indicators characterizing bioeconomy at the regional level.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Aggregate data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1000

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The aggregated data is not available

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Any software able to open data file

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

The costs are covered by the project funding.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Anna Kubule (0000-0002-0518-3163)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

Powered by

